

Leveraging Technology to Enhance Learning for Out-Of-School Persons: A Structure for Inclusive Education

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Millions of Nigerian children and young adults lack access to formal education, leading to a concerning annual increase in this population. It is the responsibility of government officials, policy makers, and educators to offer flexible education options to all citizens, removing barriers to educational access. This study examines the challenges for providing educational opportunities for all citizens and explores how technology can facilitate access to education, particularly for vulnerable populations, without bias. Through a systematic review of existing research, this paper highlights the lack of unified efforts by public and private sectors to address the educational needs of out-of-school individuals. It proposes a framework for implementing inclusive, technology-driven learning programs for this demographic.

Keywords:

Quadruple helix,
Digital education,
Educational
campaigns,
Youth education,
Sub-Saharan

Introduction

There are well over a hundred countries and territories represented here today. Well over a hundred different education systems. Well over a hundred different sets of challenges. But we can come together around one common cause. Opportunity.

The statement, above, was made by Bridget Phillipson, UK Secretary of State for Education, at the Education World Forum held in London, on May 19, 2025. The statement highlights the work of policymakers and education managers in ensuring equal opportunities for everyone to access formal education, free from segregation and prejudice and despite all forms of barriers. This paper briefly discusses how technology can be used to provide that opportunity, as education is fundamentally

about providing access for all people – to learn, discover, and live fulfilling lives. The number of out-of-school children (OOSC) continues to rise each year, with a global population of over 258 million children and youth, not attending any formal school. In Nigeria, according to a UNICEF report (Daily Trust, 2022), approximately 10.5 million children are out of school in 2021, while another UNICEF report estimates the number to be around 18.3 million, in 2023 (Vanguard, 2024). In addition, UNESCO estimates that there are around 20 million OOSC (Premium Times, 2025). These numbers are growing astronomically and at an alarming rate.

The paper reviews the existing literature, taking into consideration whether there are deliberate efforts to provide opportunities for OOSP and whether such efforts are yielding

the desired results. Technology being complex and dynamic, its application to enhance learning could be challenging and complex. For the use of technology to enhance learning, there must be proper coordination, training, monitoring, reviews and adequate support for the mode of providing education to the most vulnerable citizens. The paper tries to review the activities of government agencies and private sectors in promoting technology enhancing learning, after discussing the role of technology in learning. The paper highlights the significant role of each player/actor in promoting learning, especially in providing inclusive education to the most vulnerable citizens and their place in the framework for inclusive education for OOSP.

Literature Review: Leveraging Technology to Enhance Learning for Out-of-School Persons

Technology has been, for a long period, part of the teaching and learning processes. Technology at its various stages of simplicity or complexity enhances learning and will continue to play a vital role in promoting learning and providing access to education (Oshodi, 2022, Oluwatade, 2024). With the advent of ICT, and with the COVID-19 experience in Nigeria, technology has been recognized as a tool that provides solutions and enables people to access education even during lockdown. Thus, technology has emerged as a pivotal tool in providing flexible, adaptable and accessible personalized learning experiences to all categories of learners. This section provides literature review, explores available literature discussing the role of technology in enhancing learning, policy statement, if any, on digital learning and analyses existing practices for their inclusiveness or otherwise.

The literature reviews rely heavily on literature on the web and other online journals and discussions.

Methodology

Discussion and literature on technology and learning are numerous and this field is relatively new, though with vast literature coming from all over the world, especially from the advanced countries, where the subject becomes a special area of study. However, for African countries and Nigeria in particular, studies in EdTech become a rare patronized specialization and, in turn, literature in this field can only be accessed from internet sources. Consequently, this literature review adopts a systematic approach to identify, analyse and synthesise existing research on leveraging technology for inclusive education.

- a. **Database Search:** A comprehensive search of academic databases, including ERIC, JSTOR, Google Scholar, Scopus, ProQuest, IEEE Xplore, and Web of Science, was conducted using keywords such as “inclusive education”, “out-of-school persons,” “technology-enhanced learning” and “assistive technology”. Because of overwhelming results in the search, restrictions have to be made to access only relevant data related to Nigeria and Africa.
- b. **Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:** Studies were included if they focused on the use of technology for enhancing learning among out-of-school persons, published in English, and within the last decade (2013 – 2025). Studies that did not address the intersection of technology and inclusive education for out-of-school persons were excluded.
- c. **Data Extraction and Synthesis:** Data were extracted based on themes related to

the use of technology (mobile learning, OERs, assistive technology, online learning platforms, etc.), structural elements for inclusive education (infrastructure, content development, teacher training, policy support), and outcomes or impacts reported in the studies.

- d. **Quality Assessment:** The quality of included studies was assessed based on study design, sample size, methodology, and relevance to the review question.

The Challenges of Out-of-School Persons

The primary barriers to formal education include insecurity and conflict, geographical challenges, natural disasters, sociocultural norms, personal circumstances, and poverty. Thus, the global pursuit of inclusive education highlights the need to provide learning opportunities for out-of-school persons, including those with disabilities, from remote or disadvantaged areas, and those who had to drop out due to various factors. Globally, millions of children and youth are out of school for many reasons noted earlier. Traditional school systems often fail to accommodate these individuals, necessitating alternative approaches that leverage technology to reach and engage learners in diverse contexts.

Despite the efforts of UNESCO, UNICEF and UBEC in Nigeria in curbing the escalating number of out-of-school children, the use of technology to meet those challenges has not been fully recognized, explored and utilized effectively and comprehensively, especially addressing the problem of marginalized girls who are affected by early marriage. Numerous people with disabilities, such as blindness, the lame, the deaf, mentally retarded, etc., could not access education as a result of poverty,

ignorance, or delayed assessment and treatment of disabilities (Oluwatade, 2024). Children are locked out of school because parents cannot afford to support their children in the school system or as a result of broken homes or some epidemic that bars them from the school system. With deliberate and meticulous planning, all categories of out-of-school people could get access to education.

The need to use technology to reach out to out-of-school people was naturally recognized in the year 2020 by the Nigerian government officials, policy makers and educators. During the COVID-19 lockdown, in the year 2020, all children were locked out of schools for months and almost for a year, as the whole system of Nigerian Education, and indeed all the African countries, became grounded. This brought about serious concern for parents and guardians seeing their children wasting away days that could have been used for learning. It was this period that brought the experience of people in IDP camps and those deprived of formal education to bear on all categories of socially stratified citizens – out-of-school syndrome. In its introduction on the National Digital Learning Policy (2023:10), quoting Azevedo (2020), it states: Before the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, 48% of the world's children and 90% of the children in low-income countries were learning poor(ly), unable to read and understand a simple text by age 10. The global figure is expected to rise to 58% as a result of the pandemic.

These figures pose an alarming threat to the quality of the future generation worldwide in formal education. Among the challenges faced by school going persons were unequal access to formal education, limited access to digital resources and

learning, and a serious increased risk of dropout (Tadesse & Muluye, 2020, Eze, et al., 2021). The vulnerability and exposure of the Nigerian Educational system to the threat of lockdowns, which restricted people's access to formal education, brought into the limelight the importance and potential of available technology to provide access to education even during lockdowns. The Edo States government and many other governments provide radio and other technology-driven lessons for the school children (Dawodu, 2021, Eze, et al., 2021), and some universities and colleges of education have explored the use of their FM Radio outreach to provide access to learning. It was at the same time that the importance of the Learning Management System (LMS) became discernible. Other private schools also keyed in to provide access to education online, and many online schools were established and continue to come into existence in Nigeria, all leveraging available technology to provide learning at various stages and for various people through innovation. The most recent online and ICT inclined school is BIT-Hub in GRA, Sabon Gari Zaria, where training was provided for both children and adults, including teacher-training on the use of EdTech. Accordingly, both government and private sectors began to appreciate the role of technology in enhancing learning removing barriers to access to education, yet there was lack of inclusive provision for the vulnerable out-of-school people.

The Role of Technology in Enhancing Learning (TEL):

Technology in education refers to any device or software used to support the delivery of learning experiences, utilized by teachers, administrators, and learners. It ranges from simple and traditional tools like

the chalkboard to more advanced options such as smart-boards and smart classrooms, including all social media platforms and learning tools available on app stores like Google, Apple, and Microsoft (Oshodi, 2022). According to Oshodi (op cit.), all information and communication technology tools used in education are called Education Technology (EdTech). EdTech is not limited to advanced technology but includes any resources or tools that facilitate learning or research through technology or related tools (Eze, et al. 2021). Therefore, Technology-Enhanced Learning refers to learning supported by technology, whether fully or partially.

Conceptualisation of Technology-Driven Learning

Oshodi (op cit.) identifies four types of learning that are assisted or supported by technology: These are Synchronous, Asynchronous, Linear, and Collaborative learning. Synchronous Learning refers to a group of learners learning at the same time through interaction and exchange in real-time online with such tools like zoom or Google class, and Asynchronous refers to a situation in which the learner, the teacher and other participants are not engaged at the same time but could however be engaged at individual rates with the same learning materials and contents but at their own pace, without interaction and direct exchange, e.g. Learning through YouTube, recorded classes or an instructor's blog (this is known as adaptive learning). Linear learning refers to the use of designed programs on learning platforms where participants engage with the platform to learn on their own and at their own pace and speed, involving the use of animation, recorded simulations and videos, and virtual realities. Collaborative learning

uses EdTech tools to allow learners to engage with their peers in a group to complete learning tasks meant for group collaboration and tailored towards developing critical thinking. In this regard, Technology Enhanced Learning (TEL) provides a wide range of activities with the support of professional instructors, educators, and administrators using technology in delivering learning experiences, with learners engaged in various ways to access such educational provisions, which enhance their participation and acquisition of learning experiences with greater learning outcomes.

These classification of learning highlights a comprehensive understanding of the various stages in which learners are involved in the learning processes with technology performing vital roles.

Technology Enhanced Learning (TEL)

TEL encompasses the use of technology such as mobile devices, online platforms, software apps found on the Play Store, and other multimedia resources adopted for learning. These are in addition to the traditional technological tools found in educational technology laboratories, such as Opaque and Overhead Projectors, enlargement by Grid Machine, Audio Recorder & Player (ARP), Audio-Video Recorder (AVR), etc. These tools have the potential to increase access to learning, especially in such remote areas that have hitherto had poor access to formal education (Bakia et al, 2012). They can also facilitate personalized learning programs and experiences, serving personalized learning needs, requirements, and preferences (Kearns, 2018). These technologies, enhancing learning tools, can also foster an interactive and engaging environment,

enhancing motivation, real-time experience, and participation (Wouters et al., 2013).

Therefore, Technology plays some vital roles in enhancing learning both in developed and developing countries, particularly in Africa and Nigeria. Some of the key roles (Linda, 2025; Human Capital Hub, 2025) are:

a) **Access to Information and Qualitative Education:**

Access to information about various opportunities for accessing formal education is available to students and learners through technology, and provides various alternatives for choice and personalized preferences. Through technology, students can get information on almost all major universities across the globe that offer learning opportunities for foreign students, including scholarships and modes of learning, either physical or virtual learning programs. Access to information could also provide clues to personalized and specialized learning opportunities for all categories of learners.

b) **Interactive Learning:** interactive learning is enacted through the use of technology by bringing students, teachers, and experts from various fields in collaboration to facilitate learning experiences through exchange and synergy, such as virtual simulation, online quizzes, educational games, and other engagements, thus promoting global interaction and knowledge sharing.

c) **Personalized Learning:** It was earlier stated that some individuals with personal challenges would opt for personalized and specialized learning processes, and such individuals with physical, mental, or emotional challenges would have to go through a personalized learning process to acquire education through formal means. Personalised learning provides learning

experiences designed to meet the personal needs and learning styles of the learners with special requirements. This helps learners with learning challenges and supports them to grow at their own pace and improve or concentrate on areas where they need support to improve. Thus, adaptive learning platforms and some LMS use algorithms to design educational content to each learner's needs and pace, enhancing comprehension, qualitative, and relevant learning outcomes. Some software Apps are designed to facilitate graded modular learning experiences, which encourage learners to move on from one stage to another at their own pace and still compete with other learners on the same pedestal in achieving learning goals.

d) Collaboration and Communication:

Technology facilitates seamless communication and collaboration between students from one university or institution in the same country or across countries for the exchange of learning experiences and collaboration. This enhances learning by sharing and understanding complex concepts and their various applications, thus providing learners with a wider understanding of concepts in pure and applied sciences, including social sciences. Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) explore the potential of technology in organizing International Conferences facilitated by technology, powered by the internet, one of which this paper will be presented. Collaborations with scholars from universities across the globe in organizing International Conferences and workshops are only made possible through the use of technology, especially communication technology. Thus, teamwork, shared responsibilities, role

playing, and healthy competition are enhanced and promoted by communication technology, which further enhances learning.

e) **Remote/Distant Learning:** The COVID-19 experience in 2020 provides an experience for remote or distant learning. Both learners, teachers, and experts were brought together using technology to enhance learning. For instance, in early 2021, students of Federal University of Education Zaria (then Federal College of Education) were engaged through the FM Radio of the institution to reach out to the students. During the sessions, the radio programs presenters collaborated with the Lecturers to present a seamless radio lecture on various courses offered by the students, especially such courses that were offered by a large number of students. Other software applications that provide for remote learning and serve as personalized learning technology are Alison Online Education App, Educate – Online Classroom App, edX: Courses by Harvard & MIT, Great Learning: Online Courses, EduRev Exam Preparation App, uLesson Educational App, and MyStudyLife: Study Planner (Darling-Hammond, et al. 2020). These are quite different from the multiple AI applications we have in Google and Apple Stores. Technology, therefore, enhances learning even in the absence of basic movement facilities or with any devastating barriers.

f) **Assessment and Feedback:** digital tools allow for instant assessment and feedback, allowing educators to identify learners' weaknesses and the required support to make up for learning inadequacies. This also helps in identifying learners with special needs for immediate referral and

provision of adequate and relevant support for the learner to participate and access useful learning experiences. Instant assessment and feedback also help educators to vary and change their methods of engaging and facilitating learning in the classroom. It helps identify teachers' weaknesses and strengths in pedagogical presentation and the impact of their teaching profession on facilitating learning.

- g) **Career Readiness:** in this era of the fourth industrial revolution where Corporate Darwinian and Market-driven choices are prominent and most valuable, learners must be adequately equipped with not only digital skills but also critical thinking to be able to sell in the modern competitive labor market, otherwise they are bound to remain perpetually handicapped in the era of digital economy and ICT-Cognitive driven market, where the stronger and smart you carry out your task, the better you survive in smart cities and smart ecology. This enhances learners' career prospects and adaptability.

Thus, the role of technology in enhancing learning cannot be underplayed. It has a long-standing history as old as teaching itself. It grows and takes its shape over the years, from simplicity in use of the chalkboard, local crafts, excursions, drawings, use of flash-cards, etc., to the present complex use of smart boards, screens, electronic devices, software, and internet facilities. Learning becomes faster and more permanent in learners who are involved in various learning activities, motivating them to be more inquisitive and hungrier for learning. Individual learning needs and styles are met and made easy through technology.

Therefore, technology could be used innovatively to provide opportunities for access to education always and for all situations, thereby breaking most barriers to education and Nigerians are not found wanting in this regard.

Technology and Learning in Nigeria:

Example of Successful Tools

Technology integration in Nigerian schools is improving, with urban schools adopting computer labs, tablets, and online learning platforms. However, technology implementation varies nationwide, with some schools lacking infrastructure and teachers facing challenges in incorporating technology. Despite government initiatives, progress is slow, highlighting existing gaps in technology integration in Nigerian education (Scholar, 2024). Technology, especially ICT, plays a significant role in revolutionizing education through e-learning facilities and addresses challenges of a shortage of teachers, inadequate facilities, limited access to formal education, and the availability of required skills and learning experiences. By leveraging technology in education, Nigeria, and indeed African countries, can improve and expand learning outcomes, increase access to education, and prepare learners with relevant and adequate skills for the challenging and competitive digital age and world. Considering technology-enhanced learning around the world and its success rate, countries such as the United States, the United Kingdom, and South Korea, which notably integrated technology into their educational systems, are of great interest: they utilize tools such as

a. Adaptive Learning Technology:

These are tools designed to meet individualized learning needs, abilities, and learning styles. They also cover such facilities that support the learning abilities of persons living with

disabilities or health challenges (Kezar, 2017). This approach uses algorithms and data analysis, as earlier stated, to adjust the difficulty level, content, and pace of learning materials in real-time, providing a more personalized and effective learning experience (Brusilovsky, 1999). Key features of Adaptive Learning Technology include Personalizing using data and analytic to create personalized learning plans, such as graded modular learning plans for each student or students with similar learning abilities and styles (Kearns, 2018); Real-Time feedback is another feature of an adaptive learning system that provides immediate feedback and assessment, enabling both educators and students to track their progress and identify areas that require attention, support and improvement (Shute, 2008); these two features make Adaptive Learning Technology to be Dynamic in Content, which means that difficulty level and content of learning materials are based on students' performance and learning style (Kezar, 2107). Thus, learning content for the blind will be different from the learning content and materials for the deaf and the crippled or the mentally retarded learner.

Some Tools and Learning Platforms:

- i. **DreamBox Learning:** This is an online mathematics learning platform that uses adaptive technology to provide personalized learning experiences for students. It provides for the rudiments in learning mathematics in stages and upgrades the learning levels based on the performance of the learners, conquering each level or stage.
- ii. **Khan Academy:** This is also an online learning platform that uses an adaptive system to provide a wide range of personalized learning experiences in various subjects. It is a learning tool for students, teachers, and learners of all ages. Salman Khan was founder of the

learning platform in 2008 and it has since become one of the most popular online learning platforms in the world. Subjects taught using the Khan Academy include Mathematics, covering topics from basic arithmetic to advanced calculus, algebra, geometry, trigonometry, and statistics (Khan Academy, n.d.); Science is another subject in the Khan Academy platform, which covers areas in Physics, Biology, Chemistry, and Earth Science. Other subjects are computing. Arts and Humanities, including Economics and Finance. Khan Academy features video lectures, practice exercises, a personalized learning dashboard, and badges and points (Khan 2012).

- iii. **Smart Sparrow** is an adaptive learning platform that allows educators to create interactive and personalized learning experiences for learners. The platform uses a range of other tools and features to support adaptive learning, including interactive simulations, games, and assessments. Sparrow is the most popular name, using a combination of artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms to provide personalized learning experiences for learners (Chen et al., 2018). It enables educators to create interactive content through simulations, games, and assessments using Smart Sparrow's authoring tool. It initially defines objectives, specific for learning objectives and outcomes, tracking learners' progress towards these goals/objectives (Chen, et al. 2018), and delivers personalized learning experiences using adaptive algorithms to deliver personalized learning experiences for learners, based on their

needs and abilities as identified by teachers (Chen op cit..). Sparrow could be used to teach a wide range of subjects, well-suited for STEM subjects, science, technology, engineering, and mathematics. Other subjects are Business and Economics, Marketing, and Finance.

- iv. **ALEKS:** This is another adaptive learning platform that provides personalized instructions and assessment in various subjects, including Mathematics, Science, and Business. Artificial Intelligence supports the platform through assessment and tailoring of learners' performance and provides befitting learning experiences to cater to the needs and learning abilities and styles of learners (Falmagne, et al., 2006). ALEKS uses a combination of artificial intelligence and adaptive technology to provide personalized instruction and assessment. Learners are subjected to an initial assessment to determine their cognitive status and skills in a particular subject. Based on the assessment results, the tool creates a learning path designed to meet an individual's needs and abilities. Students engage with interactive learning materials, including practice, problem-solving exercises, videos demonstrating and explaining difficult concepts, animations, etc (Craig, et al., 2013). ALEKS uses continuous assessment to determine the progress of learners, as it provides real-time feedback and guidance for adjustment or advancement.

In the UK, Adaptive Learning Technology is being used to reduce teachers' stress and give them ample time to carry out other tasks. This

support is from a national hub for teachers, Oak National Academy, which is a teachers' resource that uses an AI lesson assistant to help teachers plan personalized lessons in a few minutes.

b. Interactive Multimedia Content: Interactive Multimedia Content in EdTech refers to the integration of various media formats, like text, images, audio, video, animation, etc, to create engaging and interactive learning experiences for various categories of learners using EdTech in learning (Tulsiani, 2024). This approach is used to cater to different learning styles and for different categories of learners. It includes visual, auditory, and kinaesthetic materials, ensuring that educational content is accessible and enjoyable for a diverse audience.

Here are some key features of multimedia interactive content that can be used for different purposes and different groups of learners:

- i. **Quizzes and Assessments** – quizzes and assessments are used to evaluate learners' understanding and progress, and the outcome would be used to further determine the level of placement of learners, especially in a personalized learning program.
- ii. **Simulation and Scenario-based Learning** – Interactive simulations that imitate real-world situations, which may include role playing, demonstration, and using an AI image-generating app to produce such simulations and scenario-based learning. For instance, a trial scene in a court of law could be simulated, or a medical doctor interacting with a patient trying to diagnose some ailment could be enacted. This allows learners to practice and apply their knowledge accordingly.

- iii. **Interactive Videos and Animation** – This is used to engage learners in understanding complex information or concepts in an easy-to-understand way. For example, video and animation could be used to explain double respiration in humans, internal and external respiration, and much more to explain how cultural practices evolved through the interaction of man and his environment.
- iv. **Gamification Element** – Game-like features and activities such as points, badges, and leaderboards that motivate and encourage learners to participate in learning processes are part of the organized multimedia content that is carefully produced to enhance learning and promote understanding. For example, Monopoly can be modernized and adapted to help learners understand the structure and basic economic activities among learners.
- v. **Collaborative Tools** – the best learning process is the Collaborative tool, where group video projects, simulation work, recorded practical lessons, quizzes, and assessments format, and recorded discussions are shared and used to facilitate peer interaction and feedback. This expands and widens learners' understanding and improves their comprehension of learning experiences. However, one would have to carefully arrange and grade the implementation of collaborative tools.

The use of Interactive Multimedia Content can boost learner engagement, improve retention, and aid memory. It could enhance personalised and adaptive learning processes, for it can cater to individual learners, while it also enhances problem-solving skills through

simulation and scenario-based learning, as it helps learners to develop practical problem-solving skills.

Virtual and Augmented Reality

Virtual and Augmented Reality (VR&AR) in EdTech are revolutionizing student learning with immersive, interactive experiences. VR replicates real-world environments, enabling students to explore complex concepts in a safe, controlled space. For example, students can virtually visit the North Pole, engage in field trips, conduct experiments in virtual labs, and practice medical procedures. In contrast, AR overlays digital information onto reality, offering interactive 3D visualizations of concepts like historical landmarks or scientific phenomena. Both AR and VR enhance engagement, motivation, and comprehension in personalized learning environments while reducing costs and time compared to traditional methods. Additionally, AR/VR can support professional development by improving teaching skills.

VR/AR applications are utilized in various fields, such as K-12 Education for interactive learning, virtual trips, and simulation-based training; Medical Training for surgical simulation and human anatomy education; Arts and Humanities for virtual museums and interactive storytelling; and Technical Education for industrial training and vocational lessons through AR/VR. In Nigeria, government and institutions are promoting EdTech integration in learning processes to provide access to Out-of-school Persons. Many institutions in Nigeria are utilizing EdTech, including Learning Management Systems, with support from, National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA), Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) and other

supervisory agencies in the Federal Ministry of Education, in Nigeria.

The Roles of Public and Private Institutions in Promoting EdTech and TEL

According to Oluwatade (2024) Federal Government has recognized the importance of technology in education and has therefore provided some initiatives for integration. The government's efforts in promoting technology in enhancing learning are indirectly linked to the activities of the following institutions or agencies. Despite the release of the National Digital Learning Policy in 2023, the impact of the role of government remains the same:

National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA):

The Agency plays a vital role in supporting ICT in government institutions, secondary schools, tertiary institutions, and public establishments. It has established over 222 ICT facilities across the country (Obadare, 2025), which include:

- a. **Community ICT Centers** – there are 18 built to provide digital skills development, support for start-ups and tech entrepreneurs, regulatory guidance, and collaboration with local institutions (Obadare, 2025). Some of these centers are Akesan Community ICT Center in Lagos, Ladipo Alayande School of Science ICT Center in Ibadan, Oyo State (Showunmi, 2025), ZEFAC ICT Center in Zaria, and Kaduna State ICT Hub in Kaduna, all in Kaduna State.
- b. **ICT Hubs** – There are three (3) ICT Hubs established to promote innovation and digital entrepreneurship. One of the three ICT Hubs established is the Abuja ICT Hub (ITedgenews, 2025), which was

established in collaboration with Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA), and the second one was in Kano, which seemed to be partially destroyed by hoodlums during the public protest in 2024.

- c. **School ICT Facilities** – this is an initiative through which ICT facilities are provided for both secondary and tertiary institutions across Nigeria to enhance and encourage digital literacy.
- d. **Cyber Security** – NITDA also provides security to data within Nigeria's cyberspace, ensuring the data of cyber users is protected and users are safe from intrusion into their privacy and confident that their data and other information is safe within Nigeria's cyberspace. This service is not only to protect the Research work of academics but also to protect other economic activity players.

NITDA aims to expand ICT centers nationwide to promote digital inclusion and economic diversification amid Nigeria's fast-growing digital economy. Under President Bola Ahmed Tinubu's Renewed Hope Agenda, the government plans to establish 1,600 ICT centers (Herald, 2025; DailyTech, 2025) offering digital skills training via initiatives like the 3 million Technical Talent (3MTT) program. These centers will also support tech startups, provide advisory services, and foster collaboration with local institutions and private sector partners to shape Nigeria's digital economy (Obadare, op cit.).

Federal Ministry of Education

The Federal Ministry of Education in Nigeria is advancing ICT-based education initiatives to improve Teaching, Learning, and Research. Their efforts involve setting policy through agencies, providing ICT

resources to institutions, training educators in digital teaching methods, and managing administration. The Nigerian Educational Technology Center (NETC) under the ministry is responsible for policy formulation and direction. (Oluwatade, 2024).

Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund):

TETFund, an agency under the Federal Ministry of Education, is a key player in advancing EdTech and TEL. It is a primary sponsor of an online international conference and the sole funding agency behind the conference host, TeCETEL. TETFund's efforts in promoting EdTech encompass funding ICT activities in Nigerian tertiary institutions, collaborating on research innovation, providing academic staff training and development, promoting digital literacy, and fostering creative and innovative approaches in education. These initiatives aim to enhance the quality of education by equipping educators with essential digital skills and supporting various improvement projects in educational institutions (Giade, 2019, Oluwatade, 2025, Ali & Bara, 2022). From the available and the mandate of the Fund, it has very little to offer directly for the education of out-of-school people.

Nigerian Educational Technology Centre:

The Nigerian Educational Technology Center (NETC) plays a crucial role in shaping the future of EdTech in Nigeria by implementing the National Digital Learning Policy. As a key player under the Federal Ministry of Education, NETC bridges the gap between traditional teaching and modern learning tools. It empowers teachers, inspires students, and transforms how knowledge is shared through various initiatives:

- Crafting smart policies that guide the use of technology in schools

- Training educators on digital tools and technology
- Developing engaging digital learning resources
- Supporting schools in setting up connected learning environments
- Monitoring and evaluating initiatives for effectiveness and impact. Despite challenges like limited internet access and funding gaps, NETC is essential for the evolution of Nigeria's education system. However, its impact is yet to be fully realized in many educational institutions, especially during the COVID-19 lockdown.

Private Sector as an Important Player in EdTech

The private sector significantly promotes EdTech and TEL through various means, including developing innovative solutions (e.g., Andela, CcHub, uLesson, WAVE), providing technical expertise, investing in EdTech start-ups, and supporting digital literacy and school management. Companies like Schoolable offer digital platforms to automate financial management in schools. Both the Nigerian government and private sector prioritize technology's role in enhancing teaching, learning, and research, though coordination among EdTech players is lacking compared to counterparts in other countries.

Technology Enhancing Learning for Out-of-School Persons:

Educating children in camps and those unable to attend formal schools is a significant challenge due to limited resources and the lack of structured learning environments. Educational technology (EdTech) offers a promising solution to address these obstacles, aiding in language and skill development for underprivileged

individuals. This section discusses five effective EdTech tools for teaching languages and skills to out-of-school persons in IDP camps and remote communities:

- **Duolingo:** A user-friendly language-learning app that engages younger audiences through interactive games and activities, reinforcing vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation skills.
- **Google Classroom:** An online platform for creating and sharing assignments, enabling teachers to tailor language-focused tasks for students of varying abilities with immediate feedback.
- **Kahoot:** A game-based learning platform that boosts engagement in language learning through interactive quizzes, promoting vocabulary and sentence structure skills in community settings.
- **Storybird:** An interactive storytelling platform that sparks creativity and language skills development in children by creating visual stories and expanding vocabulary in a second language.
- **ReadTheory:** An adaptive reading platform offering customized comprehension exercises and feedback to enhance reading skills for learners in displaced persons camps, supporting effective language learning.

By using EdTech tools such as Duolingo, Google Classroom, Kahoot, Storybird, and ReadTheory, educators can enhance language skills, engage students, and customize learning experiences in difficult environments. These platforms support the educational progress of displaced children, fostering empowerment and positive outcomes even in remote areas. Mobile

schools and educational technology are essential for reaching children in nomadic communities, promoting learning and skill development.

Implementation Framework for TEL Initiatives for Out-of-School Individuals:

To have a strong and coordinated TEL for OOSP, there is a greater need for collaboration and deliberate coordination of the activities of various agencies and stakeholders in providing access to education, including the Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC), though not mentioned or discussed directly in this paper. But it is acknowledged that UBEC is much more concerned with the problem of OOSC. Other stakeholder agencies are NUC, NCCE, NBTE, NTI, NITDA, NETC, JAMB, NECO, WAEC, TRCN, NBAIS, NABTEB, etc. With NETC and NITDA at the center, the following could be achieved, and TEL would become a codified system and would go further to be a basis for learning and certification:

- **Needs Assessment:** Identify the target audience, their learning needs, and preferred technologies. If learners are categorized into various learning styles and abilities, it will be much easier to provide personalized and adaptive learning materials for them. For instance, primary I pupils or JSS I students in a particular geopolitical zone and from rural areas can be provided with an adaptive and personalized learning platform in consideration of their background, which may be different from the same learning platform for children in urban areas in the same region. This needs assessment includes children from IDP camps, the ‘Almajiri’ children, children living on the waters, children in

remote areas or disaster-affected areas, etc.

- **Content Development:** Develop relevant, engaging, and interactive content customized to meet the learners' needs. The identified categories of learners mentioned in the needs assessment would require dissimilar and only need-based learning content. These contents are reviewed periodically by specialists and improved according to the observed learning needs of the children. Learning content must be relevant to the immediate environment and support learners' lives in the community. Both the learner and the members of the community could be made to identify the changes brought about by learning in their children in the way they conduct themselves at home and in the community. Local technology and solutions to everyday life should be part of the learning experiences to be embedded in the Content Materials.
- **Infrastructure and Accessibility:** Guarantee consistent internet access, device availability, and accessibility features for individuals with disabilities. Technology can provide phones, tablets, etc., with durable or solar charging batteries for rural areas, including customized learning software catering for various types of learners and with graded, modular learning experience contents. Organized and collaborative investment in the provision of infrastructure or facilities and tools could yield greater results.
- **Support and Mentoring:** Offer continuous support, mentoring, and feedback mechanisms to enhance learner engagement and motivation, and this will be offered in collaboration between experienced private sector players and special units of the collaborating agencies of education.

Mentoring and support should be provided for both learners and the teachers involved in the use of TEL tools and materials. These support and mentoring should equally be graded depending on the level of tasks carried out by the target players.

- **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Periodically evaluate the initiative's effectiveness and make necessary adjustments. This will require a rigorous and systematically coordinated arrangement for institutional assessment, monitoring, and evaluation of the overall programs under TEL. Professionals and stakeholders must collaborate to handle monitoring, assessment, and evaluation activities, including the software developers and the curriculum or learning experience designers.
- Technology-enhanced learning offers a promising solution to reach out-of-school individuals, promoting inclusive education and social mobility. By leveraging TEL, educators and policymakers can create flexible, accessible, and engaging learning opportunities, bridging the education gap and empowering marginalized communities.

Challenges and Recommendations

Using EdTech in teaching and learning can bring about greater benefits, but not without its fair share of challenges. In the Nigerian context and concerning TEL, the following are direct challenges associated with its successes, according to Tabowei (2022):

Lack of Institutional Coordination

Absence of strong institutions to coordinate the production, processing, utilization, and initiatives in the use of technology in learning, teaching, and

research. There are quite uncoordinated efforts and processes in importing, adopting, and adapting technology in teaching and research.

Technical Glitches

Sometimes, technology can let us down. Issues like slow internet, broken equipment, or software problems can really throw a wrench into the learning experience. Technical glitches are usually caused by a poor Internet Service Provider (ISP), using weak bandwidth, while most time, non-payment of subscription causes the interruption.

Access for Everyone

Not all students have the same access to devices or the internet. This digital divide can create unfair situations, especially for those from less advantaged backgrounds who might struggle to keep up with online learning. However, some philanthropic politicians provide learners with tablets to support digital learning.

Support for Teachers

Teachers need the right training and support to use technology effectively in their classrooms. Without that, they may feel overwhelmed and unsure about how to enhance learning with tech. Providing continuous and uninterrupted internet service in schools and campus institutions encourages both teachers and learners to embrace the use of tech in teaching and learning, especially now that the cost of data subscription is high.

Keeping Data Safe

Using technology means we often need to collect and store student data. Schools must have strong security measures in place to protect this sensitive information from unauthorized access. Cybersecurity experts are needed in all institutions adopting EdTech in their activities.

Changing How We Teach

Embracing technology often means shifting the way we teach. Teachers need to find new ways to engage students, which can take time and training. However, constant and relevant training will enable the teachers to leverage technology in the pedagogical process.

Staying Focused

Technology can be a double-edged sword. While it offers great resources, it can also distract students. It is easy to wander off to non-educational sites when they are supposed to be learning. Blocking unwanted or distracting sites can be a useful solution.

Financial Considerations

Implementing technology is not cheap. Schools have to budget for devices, software, and maintenance, and they need to think about how to sustain these costs in the long run. government's support and other NGOs are very crucial and required.

By recognizing these challenges and working together, teachers, schools, policymakers, and tech providers can create a more inclusive and effective learning environment that truly harnesses the power of technology.

Conclusion:

Integrating technology into educational strategies for out-of-school individuals in Nigeria is a transformative opportunity to address a critical social challenge. With many children, youth, and adults unable to attend formal school due to various factors, digital learning offers a flexible and potentially inclusive solution. Mobile platforms, radio and TV programs, offline apps, and community digital hubs have shown promise in reaching marginalized populations and providing tailored education. However, challenges like poor connectivity, limited

device access, low digital literacy, and infrastructural deficits in rural areas hinder tech-driven learning. Without culturally relevant content, teacher support, and sustainable funding, digital tools may perpetuate inequalities. Nonetheless, leveraging technology can democratize education access and empower out-of-school individuals. By coordinating efforts in the EdTech sector and establishing a National Digital Learning Hub guided by a comprehensive policy, the government can enhance the reach and impact of digital learning initiatives.

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